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A Trustworthy Local Email System Based on Exchange Server

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ABSTRACT

In the modern era of communication, electronic communication systems play a significant role. There have been numerous advancements in this domain. Electronic communication is used by both business and non-commercial groups. For sensitive communication, the messaging system must be secure. Many organizations provide messaging services on a rental basis, however, there are many hazards associated.

In this paper, we developed a messaging system based on Exchange Server 2019. Microsoft Exchange Server 2019 is a powerful and secure communications service. The university's administrative personnel, teaching staff, and students can use the local messaging system for a variety of purposes.

Every employee and student will have an email account that they may use to communicate with one another within the organization without having to use the internet. Our local messaging system provides excellent accountability and monitoring services, or even the ability to keep track of each conversation. Administrative meetings can be convened, university resources such as classrooms, computer labs, or laboratories can be managed, and students can submit assignments through our system.

Keywords

Communication, Exchange, Email

Introduction

As we enter the twenty-first century's information technology era, there is a common belief that humans need change their thinking and operating methods to face the challenges of a changing environment. The “Web or www” aspect of Web Services is implemented using web technologies. Web servers and web browsers are client-server computer programs that communicate over the Internet to distribute documents and information

known as web data.

The HTML language is used to markup web data for presentation and interaction with individuals using web browsers. Each web server is identified by an IP address or domain name as well as a port number [1]. Web browsers utilize the HTTP protocol to submit data requests to web servers, which either collect the required data from local storage or create the data on the fly, mark it up in HTML, and transmit the generated HTML files back to the web browsers to render.

Popular webserver programs include Apache, Tomcat, and IIS, while popular web browsers include Internet Explorer and Firefox. [2] Email is one of the most widely used apps, with millions of people using it every day. Simple Mail Transport Protocol (SMTP) or Secure/Multipurpose Internet Mail Extensions are email transmission protocols that are used to send an email over the internet (MIME).

The message format is defined by SMTP, and the SMTP server (mail transfer agent) stores and routes messages across the internet, according to [3].

The Simple Mail Transfer Protocol (SMTP) is used by Mail Transfer Agents (MTA) to transmit emails. MTA is frequently the victim of DoS assaults, both intentional and unexpected. A few emails might overload an email server, causing a Denial of Service (DoS) situation.

The delivery method is hurt so badly in an SMTP DoS attack that genuine e-mails experience an unacceptably long delay [4]. Email bombing is a type of SMTP denial of service attack in which a large number of messages are sent to a recipient's inbox and mail server. The email bomb might cause harm such as a loss of internet connection and other issues [5].

These situations can lead to more significant issues, especially if you're utilizing the internet for work. The goal of e-mail bombs is to overwhelm the mail server with messages until it becomes busy or unusable [6]. Mass e-mail assaults can also be used to conceal an intruder's identity, reduce the accessibility of communications networks, jeopardize an institution's integrity, or surreptitiously distribute unauthorized content.

EMAIL SYSTEM VULNERABILITIES: Vulnerability is a system defect or weakness. An attacker can use this flaw to weaken a system's security. Vulnerability is the result of three factors: a fault in the system, attacker access to the defect, and the ability to exploit the flaw. To start a mail service assault, the attacker must first identify and focus on a portion of the mail flow that may be exploited. Existing mail service attacks concentrate on ways for malicious attackers to deliver more mail traffic across the Internet while escaping accountability by impersonating messages [7].

ATTACKS ON EMAIL SYSTEM: The email system contains numerous attack points, making it vulnerable to assaults such as Directory Harvest Attacks, SMTP Auth Attacks, Mail Relay Attacks, and others that are modified versions of these attacks.

Attacks against Directory Harvesting: A directory harvest attack [8] is designed to extract a critical piece of information from your directory services, notably valid e-mail addresses. Spammers can target messages to genuine user accounts without attracting as much unfavorable attention if they know which e-mail addresses in a company are authentic.

Directory harvesting attacks are frequently carried out by sending a huge number of e-mail addresses to an organization with very little content. The e-mail messages are created at random, although they contain widely used e-mail aliases.

If the e-mail message does not result in a Non-Delivery Report (NDR), the message was delivered, making the address legitimate. Individuals or groups that specialize in creating and disseminating spam may gather these directory harvest lists before initiating a spam campaign.

Regardless of how long it takes for the directory server to respond; the SMTP server imposes a predetermined delay before returning the “Recipient OK” or “User unknown” response. A directory harvest assault becomes difficult to carry out due to the amount of time required to obtain information [8].

Attack on the Poisoning of the Cache

Store poisoning attacks [8] cause erroneous information, such as the wrong Internet Protocol (IP) address for a domain name, to be cached by a DNS server. When a query is made to identify the MX record for a target domain name, the DNS server responds with the wrong address due to the poisoned cache. Because the mail server is unaware that it has been provided incorrect information, it connects to the resolved address and delivers the e-mail messages. As a result of cache poisoning, an attacker may be able to transmit e-mail messages to an unauthorized messaging service [9].

NDR (Non-Delivery Report) Attacks

Some attacks use the tactics of previous assaults to achieve their goals. NDR assaults [10] are an excellent illustration of this because they rely on address spoofing to succeed. An NDR is an e-mail message created by a messaging system that informs the sender that the destination e-mail address does not exist and that the message may not be sent. The NDR is generated and forwarded to the message's sender, indicating that, despite the fact that the e-mail message arrived successfully at the target messaging system for the domain name, the username indicated on the message does not exist in the target mail infrastructure, which is addressed to fictional addresses in a target enterprise. The messages arrive to the target, and because the addresses do not exist in the environment, the messaging system will create an NDR for each of the fictitious target mail messages, often with the original message attached, to be routed back to the source. Until the source address is examined thoroughly, this does not appear to be anything unusual. The tricky element of an NDR attack is that each of the original messages' source address has been faked to resemble a valid e-mail account on another mail infrastructure. So, when the NDRs are created by the target system, they will be sent to the faked sending

address, and each NDR will be delivered to an unwary user, containing the original spam message as an attachment. Users may misinterpret the NDR as a response to one of their own messages and open it, fulfilling the aim of displaying the spam message to the users without being able to track it back to the originator. NDR attacks are comparable to mail relay attacks in many respects, but on a smaller scale. An NDR attack utilizes one genuine mail system to transmit spam to another valid mail system using NDR messages by generating spam messages with entirely false address information. Servers are essentially utilized as a dispatch point [11]. As depicted in Figure 4. When an attacker tries to overwhelm the target system and cause it to fail, this is known as a DoS assault [14]. The majority of these attacks include sending a huge number of requests to the target system, far beyond the system's design processing capability. The target will be activated if the attack is successful. This paper demonstrates how to use Exchange Server 2019 to manage and protect the communication system, ensuring that essential messages are handled responsibly and securely. Users' needs can be met by expanding our email system. This work uses the most powerful tools, Windows Server 2019, Exchange Server 2019, Active Directory, and DNS which are the latest products of Microsoft in the market for designing email systems [5].

Related Work

Email reputation systems assign a score to email sending entities based on their sending history. An email address, IP address, or domain name can all be used as the entity. Some reputation systems utilize qualitative (e.g., good or poor) and quantitative (e.g., high or low) measurements, while others use both (e.g., spam score is 58). [9] provides a quick taxonomy of email reputation systems.

Reputation systems based on addresses are quite common. Individuals frequently utilize whitelists and blacklists based on email addresses, such as DO Email [10]. Many sender authentication techniques have been suggested to combat email address spoofing, the most notable of which being SPF (Sender Policy Framework)[9] and DKIM (Domain Keys Identified Mail) [10]. SPF and DKIM can assist in identifying the transmitting party, but they cannot establish its validity because spammers use these methods as well [18], [12]. DNSBL [21], [16] is a form of blacklist based on IP address, which spreads the blacklist through DNS and is widely used. On the other hand, the efficacy of DNSBL has been questioned [12], [13], [14], [15]. In addition to DNSBL, there are other forms of reputation systems based on IP addresses, such as [16]. These systems are usually commercial and employ proprietary reputation management and distribution strategies. The Gmail reputation system [3] assigns points to websites instead of IP addresses. It uses only local data to identify the transmission domain, as well as heuristics, SPF, and DKIM. Singaraja et al. [6] developed RepuScore, a collaborative email reputation architecture that rates domains as well. By examining the SMTP sending path (in the email header) of known genuine emails and spam emails, Leba et al. [17] presented a method to derive the reputation of email domains and IP addresses. Golbeck et al. [18] presented a method that uses the exchange of reputation values to deduce the relative reputation ratings of email contacts. Chirita et al. [19] created MailRank, a reputation method that can compute both global and customized reputation

scores for each email account. Both [18] and [19] presuppose the presence of a worldwide email social network and use a centralized method to compute reputation ratings. Spam signature creation and email address whitelisting have both benefited from the collaboration. Vipul's razor [20] is a collaborative network for submitting and disseminating human-identified spam signatures. LOAF [21], FOAF [22], and RE: [23] were created to automatically increase the whitelist. These methods rely on social ties to determine the sender's and recipient's indirect relationship.

The author talked about cyberattacks in [24], which is a framework for defending against attacks. The countermeasure is setting the MTA to accept and queue SMTP mail, processing the message using rule-based filters, and then forwarding the message once it has been filtered. For a significant subset of email bombs, it provides a filtering mechanism that is both simple and effective. The prototype filter script is implemented by the author. In order to combat Internet mail bombs, a mix of black hole strategy, fast prototyping, deployment of rule-based filters, and thorough understanding of the battlespace is useful. [25] Gomez et al. Spam, anomalous mail, and aggregated mail are the three types of e-mail traffic near big institutions, and each task is then classified individually. Their objective is to uncover spam traffic characteristics that may be utilized to create more effective spam control solutions in the future.

Disadvantages of the existing system

Information is delayed.

Lack of security.

It is time-consuming to inquire with the messaging service provider.

The email is not confidential because it passes through the service provider.

Email is not under the direct control of the organization.

Damage to records due to lack of interest from service providers.

Materials and Methods

EXPECTED WORK

The proposed system's results and benefits include time savings, improved communication, more security, and lower maintenance costs.

Distributed immoral elements are posing a growing security danger to email systems. Many attacks appear to have been carried out through the Web environment. As a result, we present a technique for detecting and preventing some of these assaults, resulting in improved performance.

Proposed System

The approach and implementation of the system are both commonly perceived. The system only uses a little number of resources and may be used in essentially any configuration. The functions are performed [2]. Easy to use, save time, better service, easy access, higher efficiency, ensure data accuracy, user-friendly GUI interface, reduce record damage. And appropriately control superior officials.

Preliminary Investigation

The objective of the preliminary inquiry is to analyze the proposed requirements. The information obtained allows for an informal assessment of the project request's merit and educated judgements about the project's potential for preliminary investigations based on the information gathered2].

Modes of the Requirement Elicitation

Interviews

Written Documents of non-governmental organizations show how the system should operate? But still they don't include enough details to decide about the merits of the proposed system. Also, they did not present user views about current system. Non-governmental groups' written documents demonstrate how the system should work? However, lack sufficient details to assess the proposed system's advantages also failed to include user feedback on the current system.

Areas Required to Be Focused Pieces

The framework can be used to evaluate a problem's urgency or the effectiveness of a solution.

Performance

The system provides sufficient security and response time.

Information

The system offers adequate services level and capacity that reduces the costs or increases the profit of the system.

Efficiency

The system provides adequate control to secure and ensure data and information correctness and security.

Service

The system is flexible and adaptive although it provides ideal and dependable services to all those who enable.

Figure 1: Proposed Messaging System

System Design

The proposed system depicts the entire local email system design. A domain environment is required for Exchange Server 2019 to function correctly. In Windows Server 2019, we developed a domain, DHCP, DNS, and Active Directory. To connect to other departments, the local e-mail system is implemented and connected to the university or organization's central exchange. Each department has its own switch, which is in turn connected to the main switch. The local email system provides each employee and student with an email account that they may access from anywhere within the domain. The message administrator has total control over the local system's email.

Windows Server 2019

Windows Server 2019 Foundation is a 64-bit version of Windows® Server that supports file and print sharing, remote access, and security. It provides a network foundation on which you can manage the settings on a computer running the Windows operating system from a centrally located, as well as run the most popular commercial applications. It also provides a familiar Windows user interface to assist you in managing users and safeguarding company data.

So, don't even have to install new hardware and operating systems separately although Windows Server 2019 Foundation has it pre-installed. Windows Server 2019 Foundation is supported by a growing community of

experienced professionals that can help out manage the Windows Server network. [3]

The most significant changes in Server 2019 management can be classified into two parts: Server Manager and Windows PowerShell. Since Windows Server 2019, Server Manager has featured, and PowerShell has functioned since Windows Server 2019. Both evolutions have been a microcosm of many other Microsoft technologies aimed at IT professionals. Both began on a modest scale and were easily discarded by the most of system administrators. Nevertheless, as diverse technical skills develop, it is getting increasingly difficult to address. We began to rely on them more frequently. In Server 2019, both are now at the core of server management. [2]

DHCP Server

For system administrators, DHCP provides flexibility or management convenience. Manual IP configuration is to assign the properties of the network adapter and manually set the IP address, usually called a static IP address. It is easy to manually assign IP addresses to a group of 5-10 computers. On the other hand, it is quite difficult to manually assign IP addresses in a large environment with 1,000 computers. There has to be a simple way to accomplish this, and the simplest one is to utilize a DHCP server. The IP address is automatically assigned to the client computer via DHCP or automated IP setup, and this is referred to as a dynamic IP address. When a computer first needs an IP address from DHCP, it does not have a DHCP IP address or its IP address, so it broadcasts a DHCP Discover packet over the network. All devices on a network get these DHCP discovery packets. Even though port number 68 is included in this packet, if the DHCP server is in the client's broadcast domain, it will accept the client's request and assign an IPv4 IP address to the client. The communication between the client and the DHCP server takes place in four stages, which are referred to as DORA (discover, provide, request, confirm)[6].

Client Broadcast DHCP Discover Packet

The client computer sends a message over the network to identify the DHCP server in the first stage. The client's computer broadcasts this message, which is known as a DHCP discovery message. When the client does not know the DHCP server's IP address, the only way to communicate with the client and recognize the DHCP server's IP address is to broadcast.

DHCP Server Broadcast DHCP Offer Packet to the client

in the second stage, When the DHCP server receives the client's DHCP Discover message, it responds by sending a message to the client that includes terms and conditions and an available IP address, which is referred as DHCP Offer.

DHCP Client send a DHCP request message to the DHCP server

Whenever the client computer receives an offer from the DHCP server, it accepts the offer and requests that the DHCP server provide the IP address that include in the DHCP offer message in the third stage.

DHCP Server sends a DHCP Ack message to the DHCP client

So when the DHCP server receives the client request message in the fourth stage. The DHCP server next checks the pool for the requested IP address's availability, and if it's still accessible, it sends an Ack

(confirmation) message to the client, allowing users to use that IP address. [6].

DNS Server

The Domain Name System (DNS) is a system that converts names into IP addresses or name resolution. Active Directory cannot function without DNS. DNS is a service that translates computer names into IP addresses. DNS is based on a hierarchical structure (house#10 street-1 model town Lahore Punjab Pakistan), rather than an apartment-based approach (house#10, house#12, etc.). FQDN is used by DNS (Fully Qualified Domain Name). DNS simply provides the IP address to others. DNS is an application layer protocol that employs both TCP and UDP. DNS has a port number of 53. [7] Although IP addresses are more difficult to remember than names, users use names instead of IP addresses when communicating with computers. For instance, www.yahoo.com. The name was developed only for the benefit of mankind. To go to the destination, it's translated to an IP address. Name resolution is the process of translating a name. The process of resolving names starts on the right and works its way to the left. After com, there is another "." that is hidden. The root-level domain is the name given to this point. When a request for translation is forwarded to the root domain, it is sent to the com domain, popularly referred as the top-level domain. The request to a Yahoo domain known as a secondary domain is included. The request is subsequently sent to www, which is known as the hostname. Over the Internet, the DNS structure is distributed (the entire database is not in one location) rather than centralized (the entire database is in one location). That ensures that name resolution tasks are distributed across the Internet, not just among DNS server computers across the world, since if this DNS goes down, the entire Internet will be inaccessible. [8].

DNS Queries

A request to DNS is referred to as a query. DNS queries illustrate how clients request IP addresses and how DNS servers respond to them.

Types of queries Recursive Query

It proceeds from the DNS client to the DNS server. The "complete" response indicates that the operation is complete. That indicates that if a user requests DNS for a computer's IP address, it will either return the IP address or the name not found[23].

Iterative Query

It proceeds from one DNS server to the next. Its incomplete response indicates that it is a recommendation. To turn from one DNS to another, iterative queries are utilized. It can keep the response for 60 minutes in its cache[23].

Inverse Query

It serves as a form of security. Whenever users restrict websites based on their name and client type IP address, the proxy server (firewall, AISA) sends the IP address to the DNS server and requests the name based on the name. Enter the command prompt and type C: nslookup www.bkuc.edu.pk to find out the IP address of any website (enter). It could provide the user the Yahoo site's IP address, that users can now manually type into a

browser to visit the Yahoo site. [8].

Domain Types

Root Domain

The root domain is the forest's 1st domain. In a forest, there can only be one root domain. A forest is created whenever the root domain is installed. The parent domain is like the root domain. When the root domain collapses, the forest collapses as well, however if other domains collapse, the forest is unaffected. User can identify its root domain whenever users see the schema management group and the enterprise management group in Active Directory [25].

Parent Domain

The domain is set up as either a parent or a child. In a forest, there can be numerous domains. A root domain is not a parent domain, although a parent domain is a root domain. The parent domain is the first domain in the tree. A tree is created when the parent domain is installed [27].

Child Domain

The tree's second domain is referred as the subdomain. As the subdomain must have a parent domain name as a suffix, user can identify it apart from its name. [11]

Exchange Server 2019

Now, why do we recommend Exchange 2019 beyond alternative mail servers from other organizations, such as to send mail (Linux) and Lotus Domino, once users decided to implement a mail server? (IBM). As a result, the response is that Exchange is a Microsoft product. Microsoft, in contrast to other corporations, has a variety of service centers. Support for the product's success is crucial. The second benefit is that most Microsoft e-mail applications work like Outlook on the client side and Exchange can only provide full functionality whenever Exchange is installed on the mail server. Lotus Domino is a server-side application, whereas Lotus Notes is a client-side application that serves a similar function to Microsoft Office. That indicates that if a user is utilizing Exchange, Outlook (also termed as PIM or Personal Information Manager) can provide full client functionality. Using a Lotus Notes on the client-side can provide users complete capability if users are running Lotus Domino. Although most employees are familiar with Outlook due to their frequent use of Microsoft Office, employees do not require training; however, no one is familiar with Lotus Notes, moreover, employees must be educated. The messaging system or the information delivery system must also require some catalog systems in parallel. If you take a mobile phone as an example, then the address book is the address book system of the mobile phone, and the mobile phone itself is an information transmission system. The directory system of the exchange server is Active Directory, which stores all user accounts that can use the exchange server. If there is no Active Directory, you will not be able to exchange. In early versions 4, 5.0, and 5.5, there was an exchange service called an exchange directory service, but now exchange is completely dependent on Active Directory. [12]. A real-time copy called DAG (Database Availability Group) is one of the new features of Microsoft Exchange Server 2019. It is more dependable than Exchange 2016. Since it includes additional

filters, Exchange 2019 is more secure than previous versions. OWA (Outlook Web Application) is a new management feature in Exchange 2019. Users can check e-mail over the phone using the Exchange 2019 integrated phone system. Another new feature is RBAC (Role-Based Access Control). [7] Management can be done in three sections in Exchange 2019. Exchange Management Console (EMC): Exchange command line management program (command line) Exchange Control Panel (ECP): Exchange Management Console (EMC): It is a new feature of Exchange 2019 that enables users to use the Exchange management form ECP (<https://pc1.bkuc.edu.pk/ecp>) to execute Exchange management tasks. The Outlook web access feature in Exchange 2019 was used to browse and send a web-based interface with no administrative or development support, simply email access. Outlook Web Apps are used to handle and control emails through a web-based interface in Exchange 2019 [6]. As Active Directory has a forest, the exchange has an organization. Although there can't be two forests in an Active Directory, there can only be one Exchange server every organization. In exchange, the organization is in charge of entire storage and database control in 2019, whereas the server was in charge in previous versions. When certain activities are performed at the organizational level, they influence the entire organization. The regular version allows you to build 5 stores, while the business edition allows you to construct 100. The user's mail is kept in a mailbox that is kept in a store.

In Exchange 2019, there are no storage groups, thus each store has its log file that is reduced to 1 MB in size, whereas in the previous version, there was a storage group, and each storage group can also have up to 5 stores, but each store had just one 5 MB log file, causing performance issues. The database on your C: disk contains checkpoint files, database files, and log files, among other features. The modifications are stored in the log file and subsequently transferred to the database file, with the checkpoint file indicating how much data has been moved from the log file to the database file, with the log file being kept as one of the options. The term "online" refers to a database that has been mounted, whereas "offline" refers to a database that has not been mounted. Some distinct roles or choices in various locations, for instance, the mailbox role refers to the configuration of the mailbox server, and the mailbox server is responsible for mailbox storage. The client access role refers to the configuration of the client access server, which is responsible for the client connection, the hub transport role, as well as the unified messaging and edge transport roles. The Mailbox role, Client Access role, and Hub Transport role are required for the Exchange 2019 server to function. An Exchange environment cannot be built without these three responsibilities. Edge Transport roles can only be utilized on one server, and other roles can't use them. Without edge transport, you can have many roles on any server. users need a single server to establish organization since the Mailbox, Client Access, and Hub Transport roles can all be installed on one server. If users want to use Unified Messaging, users have to do is execute the Unified Messaging role settings on that server. However, if users wish to install the Edge Transport role, users need another server, as this is a prerequisite for the role. The roles of Unified Messaging and Edge Transport do not need to be swapped. Toolbox is an exchange laboratory with a variety of features, including a best practice analyzer that evaluates your deployment and configuration against best practices, and a mail tracker

that can follow the progress of senders and receivers. Any object with an email address is referred to be a recipient in the toolbox recipient configuration. [7] The hierarchy's elements include organization configuration, server configuration, recipient configuration, and toolbox. Any changes to the organization, which is at the top level, will affect all organizations, however, modifications to the server configuration will only affect individual servers.

The five servers and their main functions

Mailbox server □ deals with storage database

Hub Transport Server □ deals with message routing

Client Access Server □ deals with client connection

Unified Messaging Server □ deals with voice messages

Edge Server □ deals with security

For Exchange 2019, there is no in-place upgrade or migration, simply a transition. RTM refers for release to manufacturing, and it refers to a product's final version.

Email Address Policy

The Hub Transport role is capable of managing mail flow decisions, although the Mailbox role is only required for storage. Select Email Address Policy on the right after clicking Hub Transport in the Organization section. There will be an email policy by default, which users can change, or can build a new email policy based on organizational needs. Instead of establishing the policy for each user separately, users can apply it to all of them at once. [5]

How to send or receive Mails

If users don't have Microsoft Outlook, can send and receive email via online apps by using Internet Explorer. Visit <https://FQDN/OWA> and type it in. Afterward when, click the login button and enter your username and password. Users may send and receive mail from this location. Second, if users have Outlook installed, open it and log in with the username and password users set up on the Exchange server to access email. [7].

Mail Contact and Journaling

If users need to create a mail contact if want yahoo, Gmail, or Hotmail account to get emails as well. The diary function is used to apply checks to verify that a copy of all incoming and outgoing mail from a user is received in the same database. [30]

RBAC (Role Based Access Control)

It's a brand-new Exchange 2019 feature. It's a new authorization framework or paradigm. Administrators had three options in prior versions of Exchange. The exchange full administrator, exchange administrator, and exchange view sole administrator are the three types of administrators. The skills of over 60 positions in the exchange are preset by default.

These roles come with a set of commands. This indicates that if users assign a user this role, but he still can get these instructions. However, users cannot add users to the role directly. If users wish to assign a role to a

user, users must first add the user to the Role-Group location. It's comparable to an ADS group. The role group has roles inside it, commands within the roles, and users can be added to the role group. There are 11 role groupings by default. There is no need for role groups if users can be added to roles, which is impossible. RBAC allows you to establish, alter, and adjust roles based on business needs. RBAC's authority framework can be summarized: [26]

Outlook Anywhere

Microsoft Outlook connects to an exchange server through the RPC (Remote Procedure Call) protocol. While RPC cannot interact with the Exchange server through the Internet in the previous version of Exchange, users must first connect to a VPN before connecting to the Exchange server from Outlook at home via the Internet. In Exchange 2019, Microsoft introduces RPC over HTTP, which helps to connect to the exchange server from the home computer by launching Outlook straight over the Internet without using a VPN. To do so, you'll need to turn on the Outlook Anywhere function. [18]

Personal Archive or online Archive and MRM

Users save essential communications in archives if you aren't going to use them right away. Important emails that are not restricted by mailboxes can be stored in personal or internet archives. Exchange 2019 has a feature called Online Archive that replaces PST files, which are used to store mail locally in Outlook. By default, the personal archive function is turned off. Exchange 2019 has a feature called MRM that includes rules and compliance, message tracking, and retention policies. The term "retention" relates to how long removed items will be kept in the exchange.

Anti-Spam Agents

Content filtering

Users can allow or prohibit communications that include particular words or phrases with this filter. It is divided into three sections, the first of which is the custom words section, in which list the words or phrases want to allow or block. The second component is an exception, where you identify recipients who will not have their mail screened, and the third component is an action, where you define what steps you want to do when a match is discovered in the mail. There are three operations based on SCL (Sender Confidence Level), namely delete, reject, and quarantine. It's only a number. If it's high, there's a higher chance of spam, and if it's low, there's a lower chance. Set the SCL for deletion, rejection, and quarantine, keeping in mind that the rejection value will be lower than the other two. After rejecting the message, an NDR (undeliverable recipient) message will be sent to the sender, and no NDR will be sent when deleted. [18]

IP Allow List

By selecting Allowed Address, Add and entering the address you choose, the user can manually add the IP addresses wish to allow to send or receive mail in this instance.

IP Allow List providers

In this scenario, you're enlisting the help of an allow list supplier to supply you with a list of trusted IP addresses to allow. 3. List of IP Blocks: You will manually input the IP addresses to be banned in this scenario. Add block addresses by clicking on them.

IP Block List Providers

If your server is used to send spam, you will be blacklisted. People will file complaints with the block list provider www.mail-abuse.com about you. This indicates that you are confirming the IP address with the supplier of the block list.

After that, you'll enter the provider's address and certain exclusions (if any).

Recipient Filtering

Suitable for your employees to leave your organization to join a competitor's organization, and you want to filter their emails during the notification period, you can restrict other employees to send emails to this employee and add the employee's address to the recipient filter.

All internal users will not be able to send mail to this employee. You can also blockmail sent to non-existent recipients, but only use it when your mail server is for internal use only, which is very impractical.

Sender Filtering

Recipient filtering is the polar opposite of this. This indicates you're putting a stop to employees who are in the middle of their notice period and plan to depart after a month. You stop him from sending letters to the rest of the company's employees. You can add domains and subdomains and define what to do with them in this situation. It will stamp the text, which means that it will not display the material in this email unless you accept it.

Sender ID

This is an outdated feature that was used to verify the sender's identity. It will use the nslookup utility to determine whether or not its domain is legitimate. Whether the domain is legitimate, it must have an MX record, and it will next check to see if the email address is in the domain.

Sender Reputation

The SCL value is set in this case. If it's higher, there's a better possibility of blocking. The algorithm is always checking to see if the user has received someone's mail. It erodes the sender's trust and directs his message to the spam bin. [13]

Message tracking

Send an email to the delivery email address, send an email to an invalid email address that has not been delivered, and track this email in the email tracking option of the toolbox. Open the user message tracking tool, and then click to select the user, and then give a name, then click search, and then double-click to view detailed information. There is a complete routing table in your exchange server. You can view this routing log on the C drive and then exchange and then v4 then transfer rules and then log and then route. You can view the complete routing topology in this log file.

DAG (Database Availability Group)

DAG is a solution with a high level of availability. If one of your mailbox servers dies, your mail flow and storage will not be affected since another mailbox server will be utilized in its place. At least three exchange servers are required for DAG implementation, two of which will be mailbox servers (since the DAG is always full of mailbox servers) and one will be the Hub Transport server (also known as the witness server), which is not part of the DAG. The witness server is not allowed to be a member of the DAG. On mailbox server2, db1 is in standby mode. When these heartbeats are lost, they will be activated, because in this case, mailbox

server2 assumes that mailbox server1 is closed, but it is possible that mailbox server1 is not closed and due to some network delays Missed the heartbeat to confirm whether the mailbox Server1 is down. Mailbox Server2 will tell the mailbox Server1 that it is down according to my statement, and then ask the Hub Transport server what the status of your mailbox Server1 is.

It has been installed. You can add 16 servers to the DAG, but the Mailbox server role of these 16 servers is required, and the Hub Transport server role of the witness server is required. [19]

Implementation and Result

First, we must set up an operating system, in this case Windows Server 2019. On the server system, the installation is carried out in stages. The preceding is a screenshot: Start the system from the DVD after inserting the Windows Server 2019 installation disk.

Resource Records

DNS resource records are entries in the DNS database that are used to respond to DNS client inquiries.

Name, kind, and information Customer requests are always listed under the name heading, DNS server responses are always listed under the data heading, and various sorts of entries are listed under the type heading. A (name to IP), PTR (reverse of A), SRV, MX, MS, SOA, and other DNS entries are common.

Stub Zone

A stub is a section with only one exit point. It is simply an afterthought. It doesn't have its database and instead uses the regular DNS to load it. Rather than a whole database, it just requires a subset of records. The NS, SOA, and Glue A records will all be moved to the stub area. The authoritative DNS returns a query response from its database, whereas the non-authoritative DNS returns a response from its cache.

DNS communicates via port 53 and employs both TCP and UDP protocols.

Dynamic DNS

(DDNS) is used to automatically update the IP address in DNS when it is changed by DHCP, because manually entering all of the client computer's entries and its IP address will cause difficulties when DHCP changes the client's IP address. As a result, a method must be in place for DHCP changes to be reflected in the DNS database. DDNS is the name of this technique. To protect solely, activate the DDNS option in the zone properties. Clients from before the year 2000 aren't supported. DDNS Therefore, you must place DHCP so that DHCP can obtain these client names and IP addresses and send them to DNS for registration. The Ipconfig /registerdns command registers the name and IP on DNS. The IPconfig /displaydns command is used to read the DNScache. Ipconfig /flushdns command is used to clear the cache of DNS.

Conclusion

Any institution relied on a third-party e-mail provider and lacked a local e-mail system to connect with personnel. That produced a lot of issues for the institution whereas when applicants submitted work and other papers to the instructors by email, the majority of customers can claim that the email was delivered on time,

but it was sent beyond the deadline. Workers, however, face difficulties to deliver on time using third-party mail providers. In order to address these issues, we implemented DHCP server, Active Directory (AD), and DNS server and installed before the local email system can be successfully implemented. To send or receive emails, each user has his or her own username and password in the mail service. Unauthorized users will have significant access to our local email system after installing Exchange server 2019. The main idea of this research is to ensure any institutions users' communication security. We do by installing Microsoft's Exchange Server 2019, which is a communications software. The network 192.168.1.0 has been assigned to this network.

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